

TESSERA

TOWARDS THE DATASETS FOR THE EUROPEAN SECURITY DATA SPACE FOR INNOVATION

TESSERA aims to conduct the preparatory work for the creation of high-quality large-scale trusted and shareable datasets supporting the European Security Data Space for Innovation.

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